

STUDY BY EXPERIMENT OF THE ZONE OF FRACTURE ON S355JR STEEL SPECIMENS WITH CORROSION

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ABSTRACT

The fracture zone is characterized by two peculiarities. The first of these is the fact that it begins after the tensile strength has been reached and the neck has begun. The second feature in this area is that rupture occurs sharply (instantly) and there is no significant deformation. It is known that corrosion has a serious impact on steel ductility, geometric characteristics, structural changes and surface defects. Its influence should not be neglected and should be investigated, especially when corrosion is an accidental destruction of the steel due to the influence of various aggressive factors. This is a perfectly natural process. We investigate the change in this area by using S355JR steel subjected to an electrochemical accelerated corrosion method. We have 3 groups with varying degrees of corrosion, which groups we experienced on tension test. We took the values of the fracture zone of the stress-strain curve, processed through the stochastic way and so we got the final results. We did a micro study and found that there were deformations in the corrosion section, which gave us reason to conclude that corrosion layer accepted stress/strain.

Key words: fracture zone, corrosion, electrochemical accelerated corrosion method, stress inside corrosion

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1. INTRODUCTION

There are many steel structures in which structures, corrosion is at an advanced stage. Some of these constructions are forbidden because they are considered dangerous and endangering the lives and health of citizens (Figure 1). Because very often these structures are not dismantled, corrosion affects them without restraint. It is clear that corrosion occurs slowly over time, so corrosion continues to develop in these constructs, and they begin to lose their mechanical properties [1-3, 7-15, 18-22] and at one point self-destruct. Therefore, it is important to monitor and control corrosion to avoid its impact on steel structures and to get them into an emergency situation. The rate of corrosion is the rate at which each metal deteriorates in a particular environment. The speed of corrosion development depends on the environmental conditions, the type (chemical composition) and the condition of the steel. The corrosion and stress corrosion are a complex process that depends on many factors such as: energy accumulation, environmental impact, action of sulphate-reducing bacteria, electrochemical and destructive processes in a structural layer [1-2, 18-22]. Although there is a theoretical-computational model for determining the load-bearing capacity of steel elements with corrosion [3]. For domes (for example) if the structure no longer fulfills its operational purpose, that promptly leads to overloading of consecutive groups of elements, increasing the displacement and destruction of the dome [4], which may establish by using an influence surfaces provide a clear idea of the contribution of a particular load to the ultimate strength value in a corresponding element [5]. It is always necessary to carry out experimental research in this corroded steel construction elements. The present study aims to determine whether there is a change in the zone of fracture on corroded steel elements.

Figure 1. Structures with corroded steel elements which is in emergency situation

2. ACCELERATED CORROSION METHOD

We choose the galvanostatic electrochemical method for accelerated corrosion for this study [18-22], as well as other researches [7-15].

We choose a current of 200 mA for each steel specimen, where the daily loss of mass (for 24 hours) can be calculated using the Faraday's formula [18-22]:

$$\eta[\%] = \frac{100 \times M \times I \times t}{W \times z \times F} = \frac{100 \times 56 \times 0.2 \times 24 \times 60 \times 60}{375 \times 2.5 \times 96484} = 1,06 \%, \quad (1)$$

where $t[s]$ – time duration of the treatment, z is the valence of the ferric ion ($z = 2,5$ is the average value for Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions of the corrosion products), $M = 56$ g/mol is the atomic mass of the ferric ion, $W[g]$ is the weight of the steel specimen before corrosion treatment, $F = 96484$ C/mol is the Faraday constant, $I[A]$ – electric current through the steel specimen [18-22].

We can determine the expectation loss of weight by using the result from Equation 1 for the three groups of specimens [20]. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Expectation loss of weight for the three groups of specimens

	group A	group B	group C
time duration of the corrosion treatment [days]	10	36	43
expectation loss of weight [%]	10.60	38.16	45.58

In order to realize the galvanostatic electrochemical method, we use self-developed accelerated corrosion system [22]. This system consists of 25 adjustable current stabilizers with adjustable stabilized current within the range from 16 mA up to 200 mA. Weight measurements before corrosion treatment and after corrosion treatment and corrosion products removal are performed with precision balance [19-22] KERN model PNJ 600-3M with readability 0.001 g.

Figure 2 Block diagram of the configuration used of the accelerated corrosion system

Figure 3 (a) Block scheme of the experimental setup; (b) Photograph of the experimental setup

3. MATERIAL AND STEEL SPECIMEN

3.1. Steel specimen

We using a steel specimens with parallel length 15d [18-22], because according the classic theory is established that the best and most reliable results are obtained right then, the influence of the stress concentration in the zones with variable cross section is avoided. Dimension and photos of our steel specimen is show on Figure 4.

Figure 4 (a) Principal dimension on steel specimen; (b) Photograph of steel specimen

3.2. Material

In Bulgaria one of most popular is a construction steel is S355JR, as we do [18-22] with the chemical composition according standard EN 10025-2-2004 [22]. We used a classic stress-strain curve (Fig. 5a) on S355JR steel [19-20] and we split the fracture zone into 8 equal parts [20] (Fig.5b) and took the values (stress and strain) from the stress-strain diagram, which is interest for us [19-22].

Figure 5 (a) classic stress-strain curve [19-20]; (b) fracture zone divided on 8 equal parts

4. RESULTS

Before we tensile test our steel specimens, we remove corrosion products (rust), in hydrochloric acid (10 min, in solution of 500 ml hydrochloric acid with 1000 ml distilled water and 3.5g hexamethylenetetramine on temperature 20⁰C), as we do [19-22]. We tensile test our samples with a universal testing machine MESSPHYSIK model BETA200-7/6x14 [19-20, 22]. We process the obtained empirical data using the stochastic method [16-22].

Table 2 Results of strain values

№ of point in mesh	stochastic result			average results		
	group A	group B	group C	group A	group B	group C
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
0	1.58156	0.87467	0.53953	1.56048	0.81675	0.59250
1	1.59303	0.93629	0.59443	1.59332	0.83444	0.60409
2	1.62167	0.96837	0.60813	1.64358	0.85212	0.61569
3	1.68749	0.98834	0.61737	1.69383	0.86980	0.62729
4	1.79030	0.99225	0.64374	1.74408	0.88749	0.63889
5	1.82960	0.99430	0.65780	1.79433	0.90517	0.65048
6	1.89823	1.01886	0.66645	1.84459	0.92286	0.66208
7	1.93650	1.04852	0.67329	1.89484	0.94054	0.67368
8	1.98055	1.10948	0.68173	1.94509	0.95823	0.68527

Table 3 Results of stress values

№ of point in mesh	stochastic result			average results		
	group A	group B	group C	group A	group B	group C
	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)	(MPa)
0	448.913	446.906	413.913	437.148	431.420	390.603
1	436.919	415.914	412.917	436.699	430.472	389.125
2	430.413	408.911	409.912	435.123	426.241	385.918
3	427.841	400.919	403.848	430.695	420.900	378.858
4	415.928	387.919	393.927	421.374	409.863	365.170
5	409.524	380.922	379.926	405.194	394.300	351.134
6	384.974	359.914	361.926	379.098	373.995	330.303
7	348.907	334.917	330.909	341.278	347.687	303.196
8	282.663	285.919	289.916	284.878	298.284	263.661

Table 4 Results of weights

№ of steel specimen in group	group A		group B		group C	
	initially weight	final weight	initially weight	final weight	initially weight	final weight
	(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)	(g)
1	383.728	339.812	364.029	226.930	380.162	208.226
2	386.449	343.740	371.703	233.468	367.692	196.750
3	385.732	344.097	368.570	229.222	378.757	206.264
4	388.184	341.005	376.780	242.221	375.559	204.350
5	386.142	337.742	376.750	236.067	377.515	204.016
6	389.885	346.488	375.753	237.801	381.403	206.096
7	385.870	344.222	384.337	242.469	365.179	199.746
8	387.295	343.656	372.591	233.072	373.743	201.754

Figure 6 Results from experiment (group A): (a) accelerated corrosion results; (b) stress-strain curve in fracture zone

Figure 7 Results from experiment (group B): (a) accelerated corrosion results; (b) stress-strain curve in fracture zone

Figure 8 Results from experiment (group C): (a) accelerated corrosion results; (b) stress-strain curve in fracture zone

5. MICRO STUDY

After we tensile test our steel specimens, we make a micro study, as well as other researches [23-26] on our cross-section with corrosion. We used a scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL model JSM-5510 for establish the determination of the interdependence of all indicators that influence the tension on steel with corrosion. From this point of view, statistical data and the prognosis and monitoring of the corrosion for the possible development of the processes under real working conditions are the basis for determining the required level of constructive reliability of the loaded structures and constructions operating under the conditions of complex and intense condition. It is obvious that adopting the strength-force methods, based on the principles of maximum load or permissible stresses unquestionably does not deplete all aspects of the fracture and destruction on steel elements with corrosion. Therefore, we used a scanning electron microscopy was in order to establish the formation of corrosion layer. From Figure 9a, a peeled grains corrosion is seen, which does not affect the mechanical properties of the steel. The phenomena are related to the destruction of materials, an unstable increase in the initial stress of cracking and stress concentration. An unexpected star - shaped structure was observed with a magnification of 5000 times (Fig.9b). The resulting structure, shown in Figure 9 can be explained by the tension of the test specimens and by the uneven stress applied in the process corrosion of the steel specimens. The influence of steel stress which is combined with corrosion destruction was observed in Figure 10. The boundary between the base of the steel and the corrosion coating is clearly observed. They all have a strong connection, as evidenced by Figure 9a and Figure 9b. Research on the relationship between energy characteristics is basically the energy theory of destruction, first proposed by A. Griffith [6].

Figure 9 Micro study with SEM: (a) magnification 1000 times; (b) magnification 5000 times

Figure 10 SEM images: (a) magnification 1000 times; (b) magnification 5000 times

It does not take into account the occurrence of cracks, but only the conditions for a critical state of destruction of the material. It does not take into account the time and the kinetics of the process, both up to and after the critical state. For the kinetics of the process it is necessary to take into account the surface tension dependence on time and to reflect processes that accompany the destruction of the samples. From Figure 11 we established that uneven corrosion penetration by oxidation of iron in the main steel alloy. This produces different content, quality and quantity of oxides - Fe_2O_3 , FeO , FeO_2 and others. Part of the corrosion cannot be cleared because oxidation processes have started in the microstructure of the steel and the formation of micro cracks in the cross-section has begun.

Figure 11 Optical microscopy images: (a) Zoom in cross-section; (b) Rupture cross-section

On Figure 12 shows the structure of the steel in the tensile stress and the corrosion condition. Except on the surface it has entered the border with the base of the steel. This was necessary to do in order to trace the state of the steel structure and proves that stress occur in the corrosion layer and corrosion absorbs part of the stress. This fact confirms the deduced formula in [3] which can be calculated the stresses that occur in the corrosion (stress inside corrosion).

Figure 12 (a) corrosion part; (b) Stress inside corrosion (tension line)

6. CONCLUSION

The experimental study found that the fracture zone changed significantly. Its change depends on the corrosive development. At the beginning of the corrosive impact, it was found that a rupture characteristic of elastic-plastic materials was observed. The next moment of the development of the corrosive effect begins to establish a transition to another kind of fracture or rupture. As the corrosive effect progresses, a degradation characteristic of brittle materials is found. If we apply the theory of thermal-plastic deformation, the effect of energy release from the atoms of the crystal lattice depends on both the temperature level and the duration of the corrosive effect (in our case). The influence of corrosion on the state of steel is greatest compared to other factors. The more corrosion is developed, the more brittle tendency to fracture is (in other equal conditions). From the corrosion-graphical dependence obtained, the plasticity indicators show a sharp decrease. This reduction is preceded by a transition from one state to another, which we can call "critical corrosion of elasticity." Our study found that corrosion accept part of the stress i.e. stress inside corrosion, which need to continued to study.

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